

Co-Designing Trustworthy Connected Medical Devices: A Vee-Model Framework for Usability and Regulatory Alignment

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Abstract—The development and deployment of Connected Medical Devices (CMDs) present multifaceted challenges of trust, safety, and societal acceptability. Systems engineering ensures technical robustness, yet ethical, legal, cybersecurity, and human factors are often under-addressed. This paper introduces an enhanced Vee-Model that integrates these socio-technical dimensions into CMD design. Trust is operationalised as a composite system property—dependability, safety, security, truthfulness, and transparency—and life-cycle evidence is anchored to ISO/IEC/IEEE 15288, ISO 13485, ISO 14971, and IEC 62366-1. The model was developed through a mixed-method study combining literature and regulatory analysis, stakeholder questionnaires (n=52 internal professionals; n=120 external users), and two workshops (n=15 expert legal/ethics/SE/cyber; n=15 co-creation with developers and clinicians). Phase-specific checkpoints and artefacts, including traceability matrices and validation reports, link user and regulatory requirements to design and verification. The result is an anticipatory, co-design framework that supports trustworthy CMD innovation by aligning technical development with ethical, legal, and societal expectations.

Index Terms—Systems engineering, Medical devices, User-centered design

I. INTRODUCTION

The digital transformation of healthcare has led to the emergence of complex socio-technical ecosystems in which Connected Medical Devices (CMDs) operate as critical infrastructures. These devices, which integrate hardware, software, and data processing capabilities, have become integral components in the diagnosis, monitoring, and treatment of patients across healthcare systems. However, this transformation also increases exposure to systemic risks, particularly in the domains of cybersecurity, patient privacy, and institutional trust [1]–[4]. Of particular concern are threats to data confidentiality, device integrity, and operational availability, commonly referred to as the cybersecurity CIA triad [5]. As highly interconnected environments that manage sensitive personal data, healthcare systems are especially susceptible to attacks such as ransomware, data breaches, and social

engineering, which exploit both technical vulnerabilities and human factors within clinical workflows [1]–[4], [6], [7]. These challenges are compounded by the sector’s fragmented digital infrastructure, legacy systems, and varying levels of digital competence across healthcare staff [1], [4], [8].

Concurrently, relationships between patients and healthcare professionals are shifting toward shared decision-making, transparency, and autonomy. Patients now expect access to and control over their medical data, challenging traditional authority models and requiring stronger assurances that technologies are secure, compliant, and ethical [1], [9], [10]. In this context, trust is a socio-technical requirement. For CMDs, trust is defined as a composite, measurable property: (i) *dependability* (performance conformance), (ii) *safety/assurance* (hazard control), (iii) *security* (confidentiality, integrity, availability, resilience), (iv) *truthfulness* (output accuracy), and (v) *transparency/explainability* (intelligibility and traceability). In ENTRUST, trust is assessed by comparing a CMD’s *Actual Trust Level* (ATL) to the *Required Trust Level* (RTL); *trustworthiness* denotes the capacity to provide verifiable evidence that RTL is satisfied across design, pre-deployment, and runtime [11].

Regulatory frameworks such as the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR), the Medical Device Regulation (MDR), the Network and Information Systems Directive (NIS2), and the emerging AI Act have established legal standards for the ethical, secure, and transparent operation of digital health technologies [12], [13]. When effectively implemented, these frameworks contribute to reinforcing user trust. However, formal compliance alone is insufficient. Trust must also be embedded through transparent development practices, early and meaningful end-user engagement, and proactive consideration of ethical and legal principles throughout the CMD lifecycle [4], [13]. As a social construct shaped by public attitudes and institutional behaviour, trust should be understood not only as a regulatory goal but also as a societal requirement, necessitating the integration of public values and expectations from the outset [9], [10], [14], [15].

End-user involvement in the medical device design and

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development (MDDD) process has been shown to improve safety, usability, and satisfaction, while potentially reducing redesign costs and time-to-market [16]–[25]. Despite these advantages, formal human factors engineering methods remain underutilised in the healthcare industry. This is often due to lack of training, regulatory burden, or perceived delays in innovation cycles [16], [26], [27]. Patients and less senior clinicians are frequently excluded from early design phases, despite their direct interaction with these technologies [10], [16], [19], [28]. This disconnect between device developers and end-users can undermine the adoption and effective use of CMDs in clinical practice. As noted in health services literature, although end-user involvement is widely endorsed, implementation remains inconsistent and occasionally superficial [14], [15], [29].

To address these challenges, this study applies a systems engineering approach that focuses on the Vee-model to structure and operationalise the co-design of trustworthy CMDs. This methodology has been piloted within the ENTRUST project and is currently being implemented in the AI4LUNGS initiative, providing practical evidence of its relevance in real-world healthcare technology development. By integrating cybersecurity, legal and ethical considerations, public perception and end-user feedback into each phase of the development lifecycle, the Vee-model offers a structured methodology for aligning technical requirements with stakeholder needs and contextual constraints [30]–[32]. Through a combination of literature review, stakeholder questionnaires, expert workshops, and end-user engagement activities conducted, this paper proposes an updated Vee-model that operationalises trust as a design objective.

II. BACKGROUND

A. Connected Medical Devices

CMDs have become integral to data-driven, personalised healthcare by enabling real-time monitoring, diagnosis, and therapeutic intervention. They are embedded in socio-technical systems, interfacing with cloud platforms, wireless networks, and third-party software, and increasingly rely on continuous data exchange within digital health infrastructures [1], [3], [4]. Their integration presents systemic challenges to privacy, cybersecurity, and trust [2]–[4]. Within this study, the systems engineering approach was applied and tested on representative CMDs in the ENTRUST project, including ECG remote monitoring devices and mental health wearables, and is currently being implemented in the AI4LUNGS project, focused on AI-supported pulmonary diagnostics. These use cases exemplify the complexity of CMD ecosystems and the need for trustworthy-by-design frameworks.

B. Cybersecurity Threat Landscape

The healthcare sector is an attractive target for cyberattacks due to the sensitivity of patient data and the pervasive use of digital systems. Healthcare data breaches have tripled over the past decade, affecting over 42 million patients between 2016 and 2021 [17]. Threats range from ransomware and data exfiltration to social engineering, which exploits stress,

limited cybersecurity awareness, and online exposure [6], [7]. Healthcare professionals often lack dedicated IT training, and cybersecurity is rarely prioritised during clinical operations, contributing to system vulnerabilities [1], [6], [8]. Effective mitigation demands not only technical solutions but also education, governance, and human-centred safeguards [6].

C. Ethical and Legal Dimensions

CMD development is governed by a complex regulatory landscape, including the GDPR, the MDR, the AI Act, and the NIS2 Directive [12], [13]. These instruments define minimum requirements for transparency, resilience, and data protection. However, fragmented implementation often creates compliance uncertainty and fails to fully ensure public trust. Ethical imperatives such as informed consent, privacy preservation, and user autonomy must complement legal compliance. The ENTRUST project addresses these challenges through mechanisms like dynamic Conformance Certificates and participatory design, reinforcing transparency and accountability throughout the CMD lifecycle [13].

D. Systems Engineering and the Vee-Model

Systems engineering provides a structured methodology for CMD development. The Vee-model, long used in large-scale and defence systems, has been adapted in healthcare to integrate hardware, software, and user interaction [30]–[33]. In CMDs, it supports traceable requirements, systematic verification, and trust-related objectives, enabling lifecycle alignment with societal and regulatory expectations. The Vee is not new to healthcare, as prior adaptations have extended it to cover implementation within clinical workflows [34]. The novelty here lies in embedding stakeholder engagement throughout and introducing ethical–legal checkpoints alongside technical verification. Human Systems Integration (HSI) and Human Factors Integration (HFI) are also established in SE, with Carayon’s SEIPS framework and Human Readiness Levels (HRL) illustrating how sociotechnical and human considerations can be systematically integrated [35]. The adapted Vee presented here is explicitly mapped to ISO/IEC/IEEE 15288 (SE lifecycle), ISO 13485 (quality), ISO 14971 (risk), and IEC 62366-1 (usability), ensuring compatibility with accepted medical device standards and practical applicability in industrial and regulatory contexts.

E. End-User and Public Perception

A critical issue in CMD development is the limited involvement of users in early design phases. Although end-users—clinicians, patients, and informal caregivers—are central to device functionality and acceptance, their perspectives are frequently overlooked in procurement and development processes [16], [17], [19]. Public perceptions of CMDs are similarly underexplored, despite evidence that concerns over data privacy and algorithmic transparency strongly influence trust behaviours [9], [36]. Additional stakeholders also shape CMD trustworthiness, including carers outside formal healthcare roles, installers and maintainers responsible for safe

configuration and updates, and adversarial users whose potential misuse must be considered in misuse-case analysis and security testing. Underrepresentation of these groups contributes to mistrust and hampers adoption. Addressing this gap is essential to improve usability, ethical alignment, and sustainable deployment.

F. Co-Design in Healthcare Technologies

Co-design methodologies such as human factors engineering and participatory design are proven to improve user satisfaction, system performance, and patient outcomes while reducing development costs and time-to-market [16], [18], [19]. Despite these benefits, their application in the medical device sector remains limited. Barriers to co-design include concerns about slowing down innovation, financial constraints, lack of familiarity with participatory methods, and regulatory inertia [26], [27]. In some cases, manufacturers perceive user engagement as a liability rather than a design asset, particularly when market-driven imperatives take precedence [16]. However, when formal user-centred methods are applied, particularly during the early stages of design, devices are more likely to align with real-world clinical workflows and user expectations, thereby facilitating adoption and enhancing outcomes [17], [37], [38].

III. MATERIALS AND METHODS

This study adopts a mixed-method approach (Fig. (1)) to investigate how ethical, legal, cybersecurity, and user-centred dimensions can be systematically integrated into the co-design of CMDs. The research builds on the work conducted within two EU-funded projects, ENTRUST and AI4LUNGS, and comprises four interlinked components. The stakeholder scope covered clinicians, patients, developers, carers, installers/maintainers, and adversarial users, ensuring both legitimate and malicious perspectives were addressed in requirements, misuse cases, and safeguards.

First, a comprehensive literature and regulatory review was carried out over a six-month period. Second, two stakeholder questionnaires were distributed: one gathered responses from 52 participants, including system developers, technology providers, and healthcare IT professionals; the other collected input from 120 external stakeholders such as patients, informal caregivers, clinicians, installers/maintainers, and general CMD users. Third, an expert session on ethical and legal dimensions engaged 15 participants, including legal scholars, ethicists, systems engineers, and cybersecurity professionals, to explore the regulatory and normative landscape. Finally, a participatory co-creation workshop was organised, applying the systems engineering V-model as a structuring method [33]. This workshop involved 15 participants comprising software developers, system architects, and healthcare professionals. Patients and carers were not included in this operational group, as the focus was on requirements and trade-offs from those directly responsible for design, implementation, and compliance. Their perspectives were instead captured through the larger external questionnaire sample (n=120), ensuring that patient and public

views informed the process while workshops concentrated on technically actionable contributions. This methodological choice prioritised feasibility while acknowledging the limitation that direct patient/public interaction in co-design was deferred.

Fig. 1. Methodological Framework of the Study.

A. Literature and Regulatory Review

A desk review was conducted to synthesise current academic, technical, and policy literature related to CMD trustworthiness. Sources included peer-reviewed publications, white papers, international standards (e.g., ISO/IEC/IEEE 15288 for systems engineering processes, ISO 13485 on quality management, ISO 14971 on risk management, and IEC 62366-1 on usability engineering), and EU regulations. Key themes addressed cybersecurity threats and mitigations, human factors engineering, data governance, and algorithmic transparency. In parallel, a regulatory mapping exercise examined European frameworks such as the GDPR, MDR, NIS2, and the proposed AI Act, highlighting both binding obligations and normative gaps between compliance and trust. These insights provided a baseline for evaluating expert and end-user expectations in subsequent activities. The review spanned 2002–2025 and searched Scopus, PubMed, IEEE Xplore, and Google Scholar using controlled and free-text terms (e.g., (“connected medical device” OR CMD) AND (trust OR trustworthiness OR usability OR “human factors” OR “Vee-model” OR “systems engineering”) AND (cybersecurity OR GDPR OR MDR)). Inclusion criteria covered peer-reviewed studies, standards, and EU/EEA regulatory or policy documents directly relevant to CMDs; exclusions applied to non-medical domains, opinion pieces without methods, and duplicates. Of 146 records screened, 53 met the eligibility criteria for full-text analysis.

B. Stakeholder Questionnaires

To capture user perceptions of CMDs and trust factors, two structured questionnaires were disseminated to targeted stakeholder groups. The first sample (n = 52) comprised technology users, system developers, and healthcare IT professionals. The second (n = 120) included external stakeholders

such as patients, caregivers, and general CMD users. Carers outside formal healthcare roles, as well as those involved in installation and maintenance, were represented. Adversarial user perspectives were integrated indirectly through targeted questions on misuse, security, and malicious threat scenarios.

Quantitative data were analysed using measures of central tendency and dispersion to identify dominant trends within and across stakeholder groups. Qualitative responses underwent thematic analysis through inductive coding, which facilitated the identification of recurrent patterns in perceptions, concerns, and recommendations. Among developers, responses suggested general satisfaction with CMD usability, though cybersecurity confidence was only moderate, with several citing a lack of visibility into data processing workflows and concerns over potential breaches. External stakeholders reported relatively higher levels of trust, attributing this to perceived legal and ethical safeguards; however, they emphasised the need for clearer communication, user education, and transparency. Notably, both groups agreed on the importance of embedding end-user feedback early in the design process and maintaining iterative engagement mechanisms to ensure regulatory compliance aligns with public trust expectations.

Descriptively, 72% of developers and healthcare IT respondents (n=52) reported satisfaction with usability, while only 48% expressed confidence in cybersecurity posture. Among external stakeholders (n=120), 63% ranked data privacy as the top trust determinant and 54% requested clearer transparency on data flows and model decisions.

C. Expert Workshop on Ethical and Legal Considerations

To explore how legal and ethical concerns can be embedded in CMD design, a structured expert workshop was conducted with 15 participants from law, ethics, systems engineering, and cybersecurity. The aim was to translate normative concepts—such as data protection, algorithmic transparency, informed consent, and accountability—into actionable system-level requirements.

The session followed a participatory co-creation model. Participants first identified and categorised legal and ethical themes, documenting them in a shared matrix by regulatory source, ethical domain, and technical applicability. These were then positioned along two axes (ethical sensitivity and legal impact), producing a quadrant model that distinguished between high-priority concerns requiring active management and secondary issues requiring routine monitoring. A final gap analysis highlighted current limitations in CMD practices and opportunities for better integration of ethical and legal safeguards across the lifecycle.

Discussions emphasised recurring tensions, such as balancing transparency with complexity and clinical efficiency with patient autonomy. Special attention was given to traceability in AI-enabled components and the adoption of dynamic consent models. Participants also stressed the need to integrate ethical and legal verification into post-market surveillance. The workshop produced a structured taxonomy of regulatory and ethical

dimensions and informed the adaptation of the Vee-model by embedding checkpoints at each stage of development.

D. End-User Involvement via Vee-Model Workshop

Distinct from the expert workshop, a second participatory co-creation session applied the Vee-model as a structuring vehicle rather than a full development process. This model was chosen for its clarity in linking requirements with verification activities, while alternatives such as agile, spiral, and incremental models were acknowledged but set aside due to their complexity in short workshop settings. To ground the exercise, participants were provided with a minimal system description of a hypothetical AI-enabled CMD for pulmonary diagnostics, including sensors, cloud-based analytics, and clinician dashboards.

The workshop involved 15 participants divided into two cohorts: software developers and system architects on one side, and healthcare professionals (clinicians and operational staff) on the other. Patients and carers were not included directly, as the focus was on operational feasibility and regulatory trade-offs; their views were instead integrated through the external questionnaire sample (n = 120).

Participants worked in virtual breakout sessions mapped to the eight stages of the Vee-model, alternating between requirement definition and validation. Each phase was time-bound, with design proposals from one group critiqued and refined by the other. Iteration and recursion were simulated through scenario prompts (e.g., regulatory changes, public trust shifts, competing priorities) that required participants to revisit earlier assumptions and adapt decisions, thereby capturing the dynamic nature of real-world CMD development.

Pre- and post-workshop questionnaires (n = 15 each) captured baseline knowledge, perceptions of trust in CMDs, and learning outcomes. Mixed-method analysis combined Likert-scale data with thematic coding of open-ended responses. Findings highlighted trade-offs among usability, safety, and compliance, and reinforced the value of structured co-design for balancing technical and societal requirements.

IV. RESULTS

A. Key Ethical and Legal Insights

Ethical and legal integration in CMD design was examined through regulatory analysis, stakeholder engagement, and expert consultation. Findings underscore the interplay between technological functionality, legal obligations, and societal expectations.

A key outcome of the expert workshop was the classification of ethical and legal dimensions using participatory methods. Multidisciplinary participants identified central concerns such as informed consent, algorithmic transparency, data ownership, and accountability. These were structured into a quadrant framework reflecting ethical sensitivity and legal impact. For example, informed consent, cybersecurity, and risk management were rated high on both axes, requiring continuous

oversight, whereas lower-impact issues, such as interface aesthetics, were considered ethically relevant but less critical for compliance.

Sustained oversight requires structured governance throughout the lifecycle. The establishment of an independent ethics committee, led by a designated manager, was recommended to ensure alignment with instruments such as the GDPR, Convention 108, and the ePrivacy Directive, alongside sectoral standards including ISO/IEC/IEEE 15288, ISO 13485, ISO 14971, IEC 62366-1, and IEC 62304. Beyond compliance, such governance helps safeguard ethical principles in data handling, participatory processes, and trust assurance.

Ethical challenges in CMDs extend beyond technical functionality and persist throughout the lifecycle. These include maintaining informed consent across updates, ensuring transparency in algorithmic decision-making, and establishing verifiable chains of trust among stakeholders. Ethical responsibilities to patients, providers, and regulators must be operationalised through system-level properties such as auditability, explainability, and strong data governance.

Table I summarises representative stakeholder statements, triangulated with their corresponding sources of verification from workshops, surveys, and the updated Vee-model evaluation. These statements highlight the need to integrate ethical foresight during requirement definition, embed trust calibration mechanisms across system development, and balance technical performance with user-oriented safeguards.

Emerging implementations demonstrate the viability of these principles, such as decentralised technologies for traceability and privacy-preserving features in mental health monitoring tools. Emphasis on demonstrable compliance through certification and embedded ethical safeguards strengthens CMD trustworthiness.

These insights support a revised co-design methodology in which ethical and legal requirements are embedded across development stages. The adapted Vee-model formalises this approach, promoting anticipatory governance aligned with regulatory standards and societal trust.

B. Stakeholder Perception Analysis

Stakeholder perceptions of CMDs were assessed through a structured analysis involving two groups: internal end-users such as developers and clinicians ($n = 15$), and external participants including patients, caregivers, and general users ($n = 15$). Distinct instruments were developed for each group, integrating both closed-format Likert-scale questions and open-ended qualitative prompts. This design facilitated a mixed-methods approach capable of capturing both statistical trends and nuanced reflections across trust, data governance, usability, and ethical considerations.

Both groups reported moderate trust in AI-enabled CMDs, alongside shared concerns about data confidentiality, decision-making transparency, and limited user influence during early design. External participants, particularly patients, expressed anxiety over opaque data flows, algorithmic errors, and weak accountability. Calls were made for clearer data usage policies,

more robust consent procedures, and options to withdraw from automated processes without adverse consequences. These tendencies aligned with survey figures showing that 63% of external stakeholders prioritised privacy protection and 54% requested greater transparency of data flows and model decisions.

Technical and clinical stakeholders recognised cybersecurity risks but highlighted trade-offs between strong protection and system usability. Developers noted the absence of structured tools to align performance with trust-oriented features such as auditability, explainability, and user autonomy. Quantitatively, 72% of developers and IT professionals reported satisfaction with usability, but only 48% expressed confidence in the cybersecurity posture of CMDs. By contrast, external stakeholders emphasised normative safeguards such as meaningful human oversight, protection of agency, and privacy-by-design.

Recurring concerns included system interpretability, interface accessibility, and adequacy of informed consent. “Privacy protection” and “accountability structures” were consistently ranked highest across both cohorts in terms of trust priorities. Thematic analysis reinforced the gap between user expectations and design practices, underscoring the need for earlier and more sustained stakeholder involvement to improve transparency, adoption, and ethical alignment.

Table (I) summarises these findings, confirming the value of participatory engagement and design responsiveness throughout the CMD lifecycle.

C. Updated Vee-Model for CMD Co-Design

The Vee-model is a core systems engineering framework, guiding the disciplined progression from system decomposition and specification to integration, verification, and validation. In this study it was re-examined through a co-creation workshop with developers and healthcare professionals. As noted in Methods, patients and carers were not directly involved in this operational exercise; their perspectives were integrated through the external survey. The workshop generated insights at each stage of the Vee, leading to recommendations for enhancing its responsiveness to ethical, legal, and user-centred concerns.

At the requirements stage, participants reframed the “customer wish” as a convergence of user values and technical feasibility. Clinicians emphasised safety, autonomy, and inclusivity, while developers stressed compliance and performance, underscoring the need to broaden requirement elicitation to include societal expectations. System definition highlighted the importance of legal mandates, dynamic consent, and transparency, alongside MDR traceability. Allocation discussions stressed explainability-by-design, modular safeguards, and role-specific transparency.

Design deliberations focused on trade-offs such as cloud versus edge computing, energy efficiency versus processing power, and authentication methods. Clinicians raised concerns about accessibility, alert fatigue, and cognitive burden, suggesting that ethical impact assessments and inclusive protocols must be embedded directly into design activities. Verification

TABLE I
KEY INSIGHTS SUPPORTING CO-DESIGN OF CMDs

Statement and Stakeholder Group	Means of Verification
Data privacy and informed consent were rated as top concerns across both user groups by Technology Providers and External Stakeholders.	Externals – Patients Survey
Traceability and system resilience were prioritised by Technology Providers during verification phases.	Co-creation, Vee-model Workshop, Survey Comments
Clinical End-Users and External Stakeholders preferred dynamic, context-sensitive consent mechanisms.	Co-creation, Vee-model Workshop, Survey Comments
End-Users highlighted a gap in integrating ethical foresight during early system requirement definition.	Co-creation, Vee-model Workshop, Survey Comments
All Stakeholder Groups emphasised the need for explainability and role-specific user interfaces.	Workshop, Survey Comments
Facilitators and Mixed Stakeholder Groups proposed a continuous trust calibration loop across all Vee-model phases.	Workshop Outcomes
Informed consent and cybersecurity were identified by Ethics and Legal Experts as high-priority ethical-legal dimensions.	Ethical and Legal Workshop
External Stakeholders (Patients, Caregivers) called for transparency and intelligibility of system outputs.	End Users – Technology Users Survey
Technology Providers and Ethics Experts advised embedding ethical checkpoints in early design phases.	Workshop Outcomes
Clinicians and External Stakeholders noted that trust should include ethical surveillance and user engagement.	Workshop Questionnaire
Regulatory frameworks and international standards (GDPR, MDR, AI Act, NIS2; ISO/IEC/IEEE 15288, ISO 13485, ISO 14971, IEC 62366-1) were consistently cited as essential baselines for CMD trustworthiness.	Literature and Regulatory Review & Workshop Outcomes

stages were reconceptualised to include both technical tests (e.g., encryption validation, latency, redundancy) and ethical validation, such as stress-testing under conditions of ageing, disability, or misuse. Subsystem integration was similarly viewed as requiring checks not only for secure communication but also for transparency, consent-preserving architectures, and ethical continuity across boundaries.

System operation and verification were considered in deployment contexts, with developers prioritising runtime validation and clinicians stressing adaptability, equity, and sustained usability. Acceptance testing was reframed: beyond technical validation, stakeholders argued it must also evidence responsible AI behaviour, transparent decision pathways, and ethical safeguards. Long-term trust was linked to continuous communication, data sovereignty, and inclusive update processes—suggesting that acceptance should be treated as an entry point to post-market surveillance and ongoing user engagement.

Overall, the workshop showed that while the Vee remains structurally sound, it requires contextual adaptation for CMDs. The updated model (Fig. (2)) introduces a continuous trust calibration loop across all phases, embedding ethical and

legal checkpoints in requirements and design, and extending verification to cover traceability and explainability. Crucially, it concludes not with static acceptance but with post-market monitoring and stakeholder engagement. This reframes the Vee as a human-centred, ethically informed co-design framework suited to the evolving realities of connected medical technologies.

Fig. 2. Adapted Vee-Model.

V. DISCUSSION

Previous adaptations of the Vee in healthcare have largely emphasised technical development and integration into care pathways. The contribution here is not the Vee itself but its systematic enrichment with ethical, legal, and cybersecurity checkpoints and continuous stakeholder engagement, explicitly aligned with ISO/IEC/IEEE 15288, ISO 13485, ISO 14971, and IEC 62366-1. Findings indicate that CMD design must recalibrate towards trust, safety, and societal acceptability. Systems engineering ensures technical robustness, but ethical and human factors are often under-addressed. Trust and safety are interdependent: lack of transparency undermines adoption, whereas transparent safeguards and evidence trails foster confidence. The enhanced Vee-model supports their joint engineering by coupling co-design with standards-based checkpoints and producing system artefacts—such as traceability matrices, validation reports, and conformity evidence—that link stakeholder needs with regulatory requirements. Workshops showed that developers and providers value ethical and user input but worry about its impact on timelines, reflecting the tension between inclusive innovation and commercial pressure. Participants agreed that safety, usability, and compliance must be embedded from the outset rather than retrofitted. The mixed-method approach effectively captured diverse perceptions, though validation of trust alignment requires longitudinal study of CMD behaviour and user experience. This

approach complements HSI perspectives that view healthcare as a sociotechnical system and aligns with HRL thinking that maturity must cover both human and technical dimensions. Future work should map Vee checkpoints to these constructs to strengthen socio-technical traceability. Limitations remain. Stakeholder numbers were modest, so results are indicative rather than statistically generalisable. While prior healthcare Vees have focused mainly on technical development, the novelty here lies in embedding ethical-legal checkpoints and stakeholder perspectives as co-design drivers throughout all phases. A further limitation is that patients and carers were not directly included in the operational workshop; their perspectives were incorporated indirectly through the external survey, which may not fully capture lived experiences. Future research should broaden participation, scale engagement across CMD types and contexts, and extend evaluation into post-market deployment, linking the ENTRUST framework with AI governance and dynamic consent to ensure adaptability alongside innovation.

VI. CONCLUSIONS

The integration of CMDs into healthcare offers significant opportunities for improved care, decision support, and innovation. Realising this potential requires embedding trustworthiness into design, beyond functionality and compliance, by integrating ethical, legal, and user-centred dimensions. This study demonstrates that trust in CMDs is multidimensional, shaped by concerns around security, transparency, usability, and governance. Using a mixed-method approach, an enhanced Vee-model was developed that embeds ethical-legal checkpoints and stakeholder engagement across all phases, aligned with established international standards and regulatory frameworks. The novelty does not lie in the Vee-model concept itself, which is already well established in healthcare engineering, but in its systematic enrichment with socio-technical, ethical, and regulatory dimensions as co-design drivers, producing concrete artefacts such as traceability matrices, validation reports, and conformity evidence. Stakeholder involvement proved critical in translating abstract values into system requirements, though limitations remain: modest sample sizes mean findings are indicative rather than statistically generalisable, and patients and carers were not directly included in the operational workshop, with their perspectives incorporated via the external survey. The framework was piloted in ENTRUST and will be further applied in AI4LUNGS to assess scalability. Broader testing across CMD types, healthcare contexts, and post-market settings is recommended to validate transferability. Beyond EU projects, the model offers CMD manufacturers a structured pathway to operationalise trustworthiness and align development with both regulatory expectations and societal values.

AUTHOR CONTRIBUTIONS

A. Arvanitidis led the study design, stakeholder engagement, data collection, analysis, and drafting of the manuscript.

A. Palaiologk provided methodological oversight and contributed to manuscript refinement. Both authors approved the final version.

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